

Table 1. Performance of ASD16 at Ambasamuduram, India, 1980-84.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill	Panicle wt (g)
ASD16	5.6	114	93	7.5	1.71
ADT31	4.9	112	88	7.8	1.50
ADT36	4.9	115	89	8.9	1.32
TKM9	4.9	112	87	9.0	1.33

ranged from 110 to 115 d, averaging 114 d. Its grain is short and bold with white rice. The 1,000-grain weight is 24.2 g. Its high yield potential is mainly due to a panicle weight of 1.71 g.

The variety has good response to the application of high levels of N, up to 120 kg/ha. Rice recovery was 70.2-71.3%. Protein content of the kernel is

10.25%, higher than TKM9 (6.9%) and ADT36 (8.53%). Cooking quality is highly preferred, with an overall taste score of more than 75%.

ASD16 possesses moderate resistance to narrow brown leaf spot and sheath rot under controlled conditions and to brown planthopper biotype 1 in the field.

Table 2. Overall performance of ASD16 in state, national, and international trials. Tamil Nadu, 1980-84.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
ASD16	4.8	9.1
TKM9	5.0	8.7
ADT31	4.6	8.9
ADT36	4.5	7.9
CO 37	4.1	8.8
IET1444	3.8	5.7
IR36	3.8	—
IR50	4.6	7.4

Seedlings are flexible up to 35 d. In addition to suitability for the first crop season, ASD16 also can be sown in Nov or in Dec-Jan. ☞

Performance of new short-duration rice cultivars at Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute

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The performance of 36 early-maturing IRRI cultivars was assessed in Jun-Jul 1983 at TNRRI. ADT36, TKM9, IR50, and IR60 were used as controls in a randomized block design replicated twice.

Seeds were sown in elevated nursery beds and 24-d-old seedlings were planted in 4.6-m² plots. Spacing was 15 cm between rows and 10 cm within rows. Normal management practices were applied.

All entries had short-statured, nonlodging plants. Duration to 50% flowering was 60 to 77 d.

Yield differences among the entries were highly significant. Although 14 of the 36 cultivars registered more than 5 t/ha, 3 (IR29692-9-1-3-2, IR29725-76-3-3-2, and IR31851-6-3-3-3-2) recorded 7 t/ha (see table); 6.6 t/ha was registered by the highest yielding check, ADT36. Yields of the 3 cultivars were between 10% and 12.1% more than ADT36.

The three possess desirable plant types and long slender grain with consumer appeal. ☞

Performance of new early-duration IRRI cultivars at TNRRI, India.

Source	Cultivar	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (t/ha)	% of ADT36
2443	IR25588-7-3-1	72	5.3	79.9
2444	IR25588-61-2-2	72	4.8	72.5
2446	IR25621-1-5-1-2	73	4.3	64.5
2447	IR25621-135-1-1	75	5.3	80.0
2449	IR25840-83-3-2	77	5.4	80.7
2460	IR28210-68-4-1-3-1	72	4.7	71.0
2465	IR29670-15-2-3	69	5.2	77.5
2466	IR29670-52-3-2-3	67	4.7	70.2
2469	IR29692-9-1-3-2	69	7.6	112.1
2470	IR29692-14-1-1-2	73	4.5	68.3
2471	IR29692-34-1-3-2-2	73	3.9	58.4
2472	IR29692-39-1-2-2-2	76	4.3	64.6
2473	IR29692-65-2-3-3	74	4.6	69.3
2474	IR29692-71-2-2-2	73	4.9	73.3
2477	IR29692-86-2-3-3	72	4.7	71.1
2478	IR29692-94-2-1-3	72	4.3	65.0
2479	IR29692-99-3-2-1	70	6.1	91.1
2481	IR29692-117-1-2-2	73	4.0	59.7
2484	IR29692-131-3-3-3	76	4.9	73.3
2487	IR29705-22-1-2-2	75	5.1	76.5
2489	IR29708-41-2-2-3	72	4.3	64.9
2490	IR29728-113-3-2-3	72	4.2	62.4
2491	IR29725-3-1-3-2	72	4.4	66.5
2493	IR29725-21-1-3-2	72	5.2	78.9
2494	IR29725-22-3-3-3	74	5.0	74.5
2497	IR29725-36-3-1-1	73	4.6	69.1
2500	IR29725-45-1-1-3	72	5.7	85.1
2501	IR29725-63-3-3-2	72	5.4	81.4
2502	IR29725-76-3-3-2	72	7.4	110.7
2505	IR29725-109-1-2-1	72	5.2	78.0
2506	IR29725-110-3-3-2	77	4.4	66.0
2511	IR29725-135-2-2-3	77	4.8	71.4
2536	IR31847-61-2-2-2-1	71	4.4	66.3
2540	IR31851-6-3-3-3-2	77	7.2	110.0
2541	IR31851-44-2-1-3-3	73	4.9	73.3
2543	IR31851-96-2-3-2-1	72	6.2	93.2
IR60		74	4.8	72.3
ADT36		75	6.6	100
TKM9		73	6.2	99.5
IR50		73	5.5	83.1
	CD 0.6 t/ha			
	CV 6.2			